

ANALYSIS OF CLIMATE THERMAL COMFORT USING PHYSIOLOGICALLY EQUIVALENT TEMPERATURE (PET) IN JAKARTA

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Abstract

Thermal comfort level needs to be analyzed because it can affect human activity and productivity regarding to climate change issue now days. One recent study to generate thermal comfort index is Physiologically Equivalent Temperature (PET). Not only using climate parameters, PET also considers the human energy balance that derived from short and long wave radiation and also human activity. This study aimed to determine the climatic thermal comfort and its trend in Capital City of Jakarta, as one of the most populous city in Indonesia. The daily data of average air temperature (°C), maximum temperature (°C), relative humidity (%), wind velocity (m/s), and cloud cover (octas) during period of 1992 – 2012 were collected from 6 rainfall stations around Jakarta. PET calculated by Rayman application and the trend evaluated with Mann-Kendall test. The result showed that climatic thermal comfort in Jakarta was comfortable (69%) with no thermal stress in most area except Curug and Kemayoran which were dominantly slightly cool. Thermal comfort during daytime indicated all areas over Jakarta were dominated by slightly warm condition (45%) where slight heat stress might appear even about 36% of daytime faced heat stress in most area. Monthly patterns showed that Jakarta has 2 peaks of PET occurred on May and October where the lowest of PET occurred on July. The average of PET showed Pondok Betung as the warmest and Curug as the coolest. Mann Kendall test indicated that PET significantly tend to increase with time in most area.

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1.INTRODUCTION

Unconsciously, comfort level in a city is a factor that can determine the human activities. Faced with climate change, the comfort level of a city must also be affected. This is because of changes in climatic elements, such as increasing air temperature are the most directly perceived and influential to the level of human comfort. One type of comfort which can be felt by human body is physiological comfort. This physiological comfort is related to the surrounding natural environment, for example thermal/thermal conditions. Air temperature is usually used as an

indicator of the thermal comfort that we feel when we are physically active or exercising. Thermal comfort is the level of satisfaction with environmental temperature conditions that are assessed subjectively [1]. Several climate indices have been developed in recent years to assess the level of thermal comfort [2]. An index that is already used by most researchers is the Tourism Climate Index (TCI), developed by Mieczkowski by combining seven climate parameters [3]. In addition, there is also a Temperature Humidity Index (THI) which was first discovered by Thom (1959) and modified by Nieuwolt (1977) for the tropics area. The level of comfort in the Jakarta area using Humidex and TCI has been studied previously [4] [5]. Existing thermal comfort assessments are based on climate data such as air temperature, humidity and rainfall [6]. That climate index has no relation to thermo-physiology or provides information on the frequency of extreme events and does not have high temporal resolution [7].

This study uses a thermal index called Physiologically Equivalent Temperature (PET). PET complements the weaknesses of previous indices, namely by considering the effect of long and short wave fluxes because these waves are not included in climate observation, so that the required long and short wave flux values are calculated using synoptic data and astronomical theoretical calculations [8]. In addition, PET also uses units of Celsius which are more commonly used. Thermal index calculations involving all human energy equilibrium can provide more detailed information in assessing thermal comfort. The strength of the index is to use the same climate parameters as air temperature, humidity, wind speed, and long and short wave fluxes [7]. As a thermal index derived from human energy equilibrium, PET is suitable for assessing thermal components in different climatic conditions [9].

Previous study using PET has been done before, namely the study of thermal comfort assessment of public spaces in Jakarta in 2015 using the thermal index PET [10] and the assessment of thermal comfort in the streets of Bandung and Riau in 2018 using the thermal index PMV and PET [11].

This study took place in the Jakarta area. Where Jakarta is one of the most populous cities in Indonesia with a population that always increases every year. According to BPS, in 2017 the population in DKI Jakarta rose to 10.37 million people, compared to the previous year of 10.28 million people [12].

This study aims to determine the average thermal comfort in Jakarta throughout 1992-2012. This study also aims to find out how extreme thermal comfort is seen from observations of climatic elements during daytime when the temperature shows its maximum temperature. In addition, it was also investigated how the upcoming thermal comfort trends in the Jakarta area as one of the most populous cities in Indonesia. Trends are tested using the Man-Kendall test. The Mann-Kendall test is a test for non-parametric data which is generally used to detect monotonous trends in a series of environmental data, climate data or hydrological data [13]. The data used in this study are daily data on average air temperature (°C), maximum temperature (°C), relative humidity (%), wind speed (m / s), and cloud cover (octas) throughout 1992 - 2012.

2.MATERIAL AND METHOD

The data used in this study is the daily average of climatological element observation data from 1992 to 2012. Data were taken from six rain stations scattered in the Jakarta area. The following are the rain stations used in this study:

TABLE 1. The rain stations used in this study

Rain Station	Coordinates
Curug	6.17 S ; 106.33 E
Halim	6.16 S ; 106.53 E
Soekarno-Hatta (Soetta)	6.72 S ; 106.39 E
Kemayoran	6.9 S ; 106.5 E
Pondok Betung	6.15 S ; 106.45 E
Tanjung Priok	6.64 S ; 106.52 E

Data from each station is obtained through <https://ogimet.com/gsynres.phtml.en>. Climatological elements in question are air temperature (°C), relative humidity (%), wind speed (m / s), and cloud cover (octas). The climatology data are compared with the data of human energy equilibrium elements obtained using modeling in the Rayman application.

Data is processed using Rayman software. Rayman is a model developed by Matzarakis [15], used to calculate radiation flux in a simple and complex environment based on several parameters [16]. The output of this model is the *Mean radiant temperature* (Tmrt) needed for human energy equilibrium modeling [17]. Tmrt can be estimated using global radiation (Gr), cloud cover, *fish-eye photographs*, *albedo*, Bowen's ratio for soil surface, and the turbidity levels included to measure the shadow / cover effect when measuring long and short radiation fluxes [18]. Therefore, Tmrt is needed for thermal index calculations such as PMV, PET, and SET [16].

The thermal index used in this study is PET. PET is a thermal index in an environment that is based on *Munich Energy–balance Model for Individuals* (MEMI) that models the thermal conditions of the human body from a psychological point of view [9]. PET can be used for open spaces (outdoor) and indoor spaces (indoor) obtained from radiation calculations and bioclimate models in Rayman software [17]. Variables used in calculating PET consist of climatological parameters namely air temperature, water vapor pressure (calculated based on relative air humidity), wind speed, average cloud cover, mean radiant temperature, and also parameters that affect the human body such as heat resistance of clothing and moving activity, height, and weight which are usually standardized in [19].

International Standard 7730 states that thermal comfort is not influenced by gender differences, obesity, age, ethnicity, adaptation, geographical residence, density and color factors [20]. Assessment of thermal comfort in this study uses the PET scale for tropical regions as in Table 2.

TABLE 2. PET in tropical area

PET in tropic (°C)	Thermal perception	Physiological Stress
<14	very cold	extreme cold stress
14-18	cold	sold stress
18-22	cool	cold stress
22-26	slightly cool	slightly cold stress
26-30	comfortable	no thermal stress
30-34	slightly warm	slight heat stress
34-38	warm	heat stress
38-42	hot	strong heat stress
>42	very hot	extreme hot stress

To test the trend (trend) of the increase or decrease of the data is used Mann-Kendall non-parametric statistical test [21]. The Mann-Kendall test is based on the S statistics described in equation 2-1. Each pair of data values observed y_i, y_j ($i > j$) of the random variable is checked to find whether $y_i > y_j$ or $y_i < y_j$. If the number of the previous pair type is P and the number of the following pair type M, then S is defined as $S = P - M$. For $n > 10$ then the sample distribution of S is: Z follows the standard normal distribution where,

$$z = \begin{cases} (S - 1)/\sigma_s, & \text{if } S > 0 \\ 0, & \text{jika } S = 0 \\ \frac{S + 1}{\sigma_s}, & \text{if } S < 0 \end{cases}$$

With σ is,

$$\sigma_s = \sqrt{\frac{n(n-1)(2n+5)}{18}}$$

With n is the amount of data and σ is the standard deviation.

The null hypothesis denoted by H_0 is a method of drawing conclusions from two propositions, namely:

H_0 : There is no tendency in climatic element data

H_1 : There is a tendency in the climate element data. The null hypothesis is rejected when the calculated Z value is greater than $Z_{\alpha/2}$ absolute value. The Mann-Kendall test is often used for non-parametric tests which have the ability to detect the slope of trends, sample sizes, significant levels, coefficient of variation and the type of distribution of opportunities.

3.RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This study discusses the average of thermal comfort and thermal comfort in the daytime during the study period. The calculation results show that the average daily PET in the Jakarta area and its surroundings is in the range 18.0-35.6 °C. PET frequency distribution shows that the average thermal comfort in Jakarta and its surroundings consists of cool categories, slightly cool, comfortable and slightly warm (Figure 1a). The average thermal comfort throughout the Jakarta area is dominated by the comfortable with a percentage of 52-84%, while the Tangerang City area (Curug rain station) is dominated by the slightly cool with a percentage of 70%. The

average thermal comfort of the slightly warm category occurs in all areas of Jakarta with the most percentage occurring in Pondok Betung rain station by 16%, while the cool category most occurs at Curug rain station with a percentage of 3%.

FIGURE 1. Distribution of (a) PET Average and (b) PET in Daytime

During daytime, PET in Jakarta has a larger range than PET on average with a range of 16.8-45.5 °C where the thermal comfort consists of cold, cool, slightly cool, comfortable, slightly warm, warm, hot and very hot categories (Figure 1 b). The dominant PET during daytime is warm, which occurs in almost all areas of Jakarta with a percentage of 42-47%, except Pondok Betung which is dominated by hot levels with a percentage of 56%. The dominance of the warm level also occurs in PET during the daytime in Curug with a percentage of 44%. During daytime, the entire Jakarta area and Tangerang City experience thermal comfort at hot levels with the most percentage occurring at Staklim Pondok betung by 12%. Some regions experience thermal comfort at very hot levels with a percentage of less than 1% during the study period.

The average PET distribution on a monthly scale shows that the dominance of thermal comfort at comfortable levels is spread throughout the year where it occurs in most areas of Jakarta including Halim, Kemayoran and Pondok Betung rain stations. While for Soetta rain station consists of two levels of thermal comfort, namely the comfortable level that occurs in April-May, September-December, and slightly cool levels that occur in Jan-Mar, and Jun-August. As for Curug, the dominant level is slightly cool levels which occurs throughout the years (Figure 2).

FIGURE 2. Monthly distribution of PET average at (a) Curug, (b) Kemayoran, (c) Halim, (d) Pondok Betung, (e) Soetta, and (e) Tanjung Priok

During daytime, the thermal comfort of most areas of Jakarta is dominated by two categories: dominant at slightly warm level, which generally has the highest percentage in the months of June-July and dominant at the warm level, which generally has the highest percentage in August-September. Different result happens at Pondok Betung where thermal comfort during the daytime is dominant at warm levels that occurs throughout the year. Meanwhile, the Soetta has better thermal comfort, where it is dominant at slightly warm levels for most of the year except DJF (Dec-Feb) which are dominant at level comfortable. Slightly warm level occurred in July including Halim, Kemayoran, Tanjung Priok, Curug, and June in Soetta. While the dominant percentage of the warmest level occurred in September in Curug and Kemayoran; October in Soetta; September – October in Tanjung Priok; August in Halim; and almost every month was dominantly warm in Pondok Betung.

FIGURE 3. Monthly distribution of PET in daytime at (a) Curug, (b) Kemayoran, (c) Halim, (d) Pondok Betung, (e) Soetta, and (e) Tanjung Priok

Climatologically, the thermal comfort of the monthly average in Jakarta is in the PET range of 24.6 -28.8 °C (Figure 4 a), while during the daytime is 28.1-38.5 °C (Figure 4 b). The monthly PET pattern shows that there are two PET peaks that occur in May and October while the lowest values occur in July for both average PET and daytime PET. On average, Kemayoran and Pondok Betung are the have the highest value of PET, while Curug is the rain station where has the lowest PET value. Whereas during the daytime, the highest PET occurs in Pondok Betung

and the lowest PET occurs in Soetta.

FIGURE 4. Monthly average PET of (a) PET and (b) daytime of PET

Based on trendline analysis, there is an increase in PET every year for both average PET and PET during the daytime (Figure 5a and b). The average PET increase was significant in almost all regions of Jakarta (indicated by p-value <0.05) with PET changes averaging 0.025°C/year in Halim, 0.037°C/year in Pondok betung and 0.96°C/year in Soetta and Tanjung Priok. While the trend of Curug and Kemayoran shows a tendency to increase but not significant with p-value 0.064 and 0.073 respectively. The average increase in PET also occurred during the daytime in most of Jakarta with PET changes of 0.129°C/year in Kemayoran, 0.091°C/year in Pondok Betung, 0.095°C/year in Soetta, and 0.089°C/year in Tanjung Priok. While Curug experienced a downward trend with insignificant trend.

FIGURE 5. (a) PET Average and (b) PET daytime yearly in every rain stations

The P-Value and slope of PET average and daytime in every rain stations are shown on Table 3:

TABLE 3. PET in tropical area

Station	PET of Average		PET of Daytime	
	P-Value	Slope	P-Value	Slope
Curug	0.064	0.036	0.789	0.029
Halim	0.012	0.025	0.082	0.033
Kemayoran	0.073	0.039	0.000	0.129
Pondok Betung	0.037	0.037	0.004	0.091
Soetta	< 0.0001	0.096	0.017	0.095
Tanjung Priok	0.000	0.096	0.014	0.089

4.CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the analysis, climatological thermal comfort in Jakarta is at a level that is slightly cool and comfortable in an average state and is at a comfortable level, slightly warm and warm during daytime. PET during daytime tends to have a greater range than the average daily PET. Maximum thermal comfort occurs in May and October while the minimum PET occurs in July. Spatially, Pondok Betung has the highest PET climatology value in Jakarta which shows that the Pondok Betung area is the hottest area with thermal comfort in Jakarta. In addition, there was a tendency for PET to increase in most parts of Jakarta significantly.

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